

Effect of Training and Development on Employee Job Performance in Industrial Training Fund

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Abstract

This research explores the effect of training and development on employee job performance within the Industrial Training Fund (ITF). The population of the study is one hundred and fifty workers (150). Self-administered questionnaire was used for data collection. One hundred and thirty-eight workers filled and returned the questionnaires representing 92% of the administered questionnaires. The data obtained from the questionnaires were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency counts, mean scores and percentages. The research explores how different forms of training and development-such as on-the-job training, workshops, professional courses and capacity-building programs-contribute to improved skills, productivity, work quality and overall job performance among ITF employees. Findings indicate that continuous training enhances employee competence, adaptability, and commitment to organisational goals. Findings further indicate that effective training programmes, when aligned with organizational needs and supported by adequate resources will significantly boost employee performance and organizational effectiveness. The study concludes that sustained investment in training and development is essential for ITF to achieve its mandate of workforce development in Nigeria. Recommendations are provided to strengthen training policies, improve evaluation mechanisms and promote a culture of continuous learning within the organisation.

Keywords: Training and development, employee job performance, on-the-job training, work quality and workforce development.

Introduction

Training in Nigeria could be traced back to 1960 due to the fact that most of the top government and business positions were occupied by whites (Olalere & Adesoji, 2013). The mass exodus of the expatriates after the independence created a vacuum of indigenous human capital. This led to the creation of the Manpower Board in 1962 by the government in power then, following recommendations by the Ashby Commissions. Thereafter, the Federal Government of Nigeria established organizations like Centre for Management Development (CMD), Administrative Staff College of Nigeria (ASCON), Industrial Training Fund (ITF) and Federal Training Centre to cater to the training needs of employees and to also conduct orientation programs for fresh graduates of Nigerian tertiary institutions.

Training and development have become essential pillars for organizational success in both public and private sectors. In a rapidly changing global environment, organizations depend on a skilled knowledgeable, and adaptable workforce to achieve strategic objectives and maintain competitive advantage (Armstrong, 2019; Dessler, 2020; Barney, 1991). Employee performance which encompasses productivity, quality of work, efficiency, and overall contribution to organizational goals, is largely influenced by the level of training and development opportunities available to employees.

In Nigeria, the Industrial Training Fund (ITF) plays a central role in developing manpower for various sectors of the economy. Established in 1971, the ITF has been mandated to promote and encourage the acquisition of industrial skills necessary for national economic development. Over the years, ITF has implemented numerous training programs, capacity-building workshops, technical skills development schemes, and managerial development initiatives aimed at enhancing employee competencies within the organization as well as across industries.

Despite these initiatives, questions still arise regarding the effectiveness of training and development efforts within ITF, particularly in relation to employee job performance. As organizational responsibilities expand, and the demand for high service delivery increases, ensuring that ITF employees possess updated skills and knowledge becomes critical. This study therefore examines the extent to which training and development influence employees' job performance within the Industrial Training Fund.

Every organization dreams of training and developing its manpower. The reason being that training and development gives employees a sense belonging. It enhances the professional and career development and the skill of the employees. It also ensures lesser mistakes while carrying out assignments and ensures Total Quality Management (TQM) (Armstrong, M. 2019).

Organizations invest significant resources in training and development with the expectation of improved employee performance. However, in many public sector organizations like the ITF, there are concerns about whether such investments yield measurable outcomes. Issues such as inadequate training needs assessment, limited funding, poor implementation strategies, lack of follow-up evaluations and mismatch between training content and job roles have raised doubts about the effectiveness of training programs.

Furthermore, some employees may not fully apply acquired skills due to organizational constraints, insufficient motivation and lack of supportive work environments (Noe, 2017).

This study seeks to investigate the effects of training and development on employee job

performance within the Industrial Training Fund. The investigation covers ITF headquarters and selected Area Offices where training activities are prominent. The study examines training programs, development initiatives, delivery methods and employee performance indicators. The findings of this study will help ITF evaluate the effectiveness of its training and development initiatives, identifying strengths and gaps that require improvements. The study highlights the importance of training in enhancing skills, job satisfaction and career growth. It also provides insight that can guide the formulation and review of training policies within public sector organizations. It will contribute to existing literature on training, development, and employee performance.

The objectives of the study are:

- i. To determine the relationship between training programs and employee job performance in ITF.
- ii. To assess the extent to which development initiatives influence employees' skills and productivity.

This study seeks to answer the following questions:

- i. What is the relationship between training programmes and employee job performance in ITF?
- ii. How do development initiatives contribute to improvement in employees' skills and productivity?

Research Hypotheses

Hypothesis One

H0: There is no significant relationship between training programs and employee job performance in ITF.

H1: There is a significant relationship between training programs and employee job performance in ITF.

Hypothesis Two

H0: Development initiatives do not significantly improve employees' skills and productivity in ITF.

H1: Development initiatives significantly improve employees' skills and productivity in ITF.

Review of existing literature

This section reviews existing literature related to training, development, and performance, empirical studies, and gaps in the literature. The purpose of this review is to establish a foundation for understanding how training and development influence job performance within the Industrial Training Fund.

Conceptual Review

Concept of Training

Training refers to the systematic efforts made by organizations to provide employees with knowledge, skills, and abilities (KSA) needed to perform their current jobs effectively Noe, (2017). Training focuses on improving employees' capabilities in order to enhance individual and organizational performance. According to Armstrong (2014), training is a planned intervention aimed at improving job behaviour. It equips employees with technical, managerial, and interpersonal competencies required for efficiency.

Similarly, Dessler (2020) defines training as the process of teaching employees the basic skills they need to perform their jobs, emphasizing that effective training leads to improved productivity, quality of work, and reduced operational errors.

Training helps employees cope with technological advancements and evolving job demands, thereby increasing organizational competitiveness.

In the public sector, effective training is particularly important due to increasing service delivery expectations and accountability. Studies have shown that employees who receive regular and relevant training demonstrate higher levels of efficiency, confidence, and job satisfaction compared to those who do not.

Concept of Development

Development involves long-term educational processes that prepare employees for future responsibilities. Development refers to a long-term continuous process aimed at enhancing employees' overall growth, capabilities, and potential beyond their immediate job requirements. Unlike training, which focuses on improving performance in current job roles, development prepares employees for future responsibilities, higher-level positions, and broader organizational challenges (Armstrong, 2014; Noe, 2017).

According to Noe (2017), employee development involves formal education, job experiences, relationships, and assessments that help employees acquire competencies needed for future career roles. Similarly, McShane and Von Glinow (2018) describe development as a process that strengthens employees' cognitive abilities, leadership capacity, decision-making skills, and adaptability in a dynamic work environment. This underscores the strategic importance of development in ensuring organizational sustainability and continuity.

Dessler (2020) emphasizes that development initiatives, such as mentoring, coaching, succession planning, and leadership development programmes, are essential for building managerial and professional competencies. These initiatives not only enhance employees' career progression but also increase commitment, motivation, and organizational effectiveness. Development equips employees with transferable skills, critical thinking abilities, and problem-solving competencies that enable them to respond effectively to changing organizational and environmental demands.

In the public sector context, development is particularly critical due to increasing demands for efficiency, accountability, and service quality. Well-developed employees are more likely to exhibit higher job performance, leadership effectiveness, and commitment to organizational goals.

In this study, development is conceptualized as a deliberate and ongoing process through which the Industrial Training Fund (ITF) enhances employees' long-term professional growth, leadership capacity, and career progression. Development activities considered in this study include:

Career development programmes, leadership and management development, mentoring and coaching, job rotation and enrichment and professional and academic development.

Development is measured in terms of career growth opportunities, leadership skill enhancement, learning opportunities, management support, and preparedness for future responsibilities, and how these influence employee job performance at the Industrial Training Fund.

Concept of Employee Job Performance

Employee job performance refers to the degree to which workers accomplish assigned tasks in line with organizational standards. Performance indicators include productivity, work quality,

punctuality, teamwork, innovation, and overall contribution to organizational goals. Organizations expect improved performance as an outcome of effective training and development.

Employee job performance refers to the extent to which an employee effectively carries out assigned duties and responsibilities in accordance with organisational standards and objectives. It reflects the level of efficiency, effectiveness, and quality with which employees execute job-related tasks. Job performance is a critical determinant of organizational success, as it directly influences productivity, service delivery, and goal attainment. Similarly, Armstrong (2014) defines employee performance as the accomplishment of work tasks on line with established performance standards, highlighting the importance of competence, effort, and commitment. Task performance refers to how well employees perform core job duties, while contextual performance involves extra-role behaviors such as cooperation, commitment, and willingness to support organizational objectives. Adaptive performance reflects employees' ability to adjust to changes in job roles, technology, and work environments.

In the public sector context, employee job performance is particularly important due to increasing expectations for efficiency, accountability, and service quality. Koopmans et al. (2011) argue that employee performance in public organizations should be assessed not only by output but also by quality, timeliness, compliance with procedures, and service orientation. High-performing employees are more likely to demonstrate professionalism, responsibility, and dedication to public service goals.

Empirical studies have consistently shown that employee job performance is strongly influenced by human resource practices such as training and development. Aguinis (2019) asserts that employees who possess relevant knowledge, skills, and abilities are better equipped to perform their jobs effectively and meet organizational expectations. This highlights the importance of investing in training and development as strategic tools for improving employee performance.

In this study, employee job performance is conceptualized as the degree to which employees of the Industrial Training Fund (ITF) efficiently and effectively perform their assigned duties in line with organizational objectives. Employee job performance in this study is assessed based on the following dimensions: quality of work output, productivity and efficiency, timeliness in task completion, compliance with organizational procedures, adaptability and problem-solving ability and commitment and teamwork.

Relationship between training, development, and employee job performance

Several empirical studies have examined the relationship between training, development, and employee job performance across different organizational contexts. The consensus in the literature indicates that training and development are critical human resource practices that significantly influence employees' job performance, productivity, and organizational effectiveness.

Training and employee job performance

Training has been widely recognized as a key determinant of employee job performance. A seminal study by Ngozika and Amah (2024) established that effective training enhances employees' knowledge and skills, which positively influence job performance when transferred to the workplace. Their findings highlighted that employees who receive relevant training demonstrate improved task efficiency, reduced errors, and higher quality work output.

Similarly, Noe (2017) reported that training enhances employees' ability to perform job-related tasks effectively, especially when training content aligns with job requirements. Tandipayuk,

Zakaria, and Mulyanti (2024) found that training significantly improved employees' job performance by increasing self-efficacy and motivation.

Development and employee job performance

Employee development has also been shown to have a strong relationship with job performance, particularly in the long-term McDowall and Saunders (2010) observed that development initiatives such as coaching, mentoring, and career development programmes improve employees' leadership skills, adaptability, and problem-solving abilities, which translate into higher job performance. A study by Day, Fleenor, Atwater, Sturm, and McKee (2014) found that leadership development programmes significantly enhance employees' performance by strengthening managerial competencies and decision-making abilities.

In the public sector context, Aguinis (2019) reported that employee development practices positively influence performance by increasing employees' commitment, confidence, and readiness for higher responsibilities. Development programmes were found to reduce performance gaps and improve service delivery quality.

Combined effect of training and development on employee job performance

Studies that examine training and development jointly suggest a stronger impact on employee job performance.

Owoyemi, Elegbede, and Gbajumo-Sheriff (2011) found that organizations that invest in both training and development experience higher employee performance and organizational growth compared to those that focus on training alone. Their study concluded that while training improves current job performance, development ensures long-term performance sustainability.

Similarly, Elnaga and Imran (2013) found that training and development significantly influence employee performance by enhancing employees' competencies, motivation, and job satisfaction. Their study emphasized that training improves immediate performance, while development fosters continuous performance improvement.

Theoretical Framework

Human Capital Theory

Human capital theory, proposed by Becker (1964), posits that investments in people through education, training, and skill development lead to increased productivity and organizational output. The theory states that human capital refers to skills, knowledge, and abilities that individuals possess, which can be developed and improved through investments in education, training, and development. The theory suggests that training is not a cost but a strategic investment that yields long-term returns in the form of improved employee performance.

The Human Capital Theory concludes that employees' knowledge, skills, and abilities constitute valuable organizational assets that can be developed through conscious investment in training and development. This theory posits that there is a direct link between training, development, and employee job performance. In the context of this study, training and development programmes implemented by the Industrial Training Fund are regarded as investments aimed at enhancing employees' competencies, technical skills, and professional capabilities. When ITF invests in training programmes such as workshops, seminars, skills acquisition, and career development sessions, employees acquire improved knowledge and skills that enable them perform their job roles more effectively.

Social Learning Theory

The Social learning theory, advanced by Bandura (1977), explains learning as a process that occurs through observation, imitation, and interaction with others. This theory posits that individuals acquire new skills and behaviors by observing role models, supervisors, and peers within the work environment. Training and development activities such as on-the-job training, mentoring, coaching, and workshops provide opportunities for employees to learn through observation and practice. Employees in the ITF can improve their job performance by modelling best practices demonstrated during facilitations and training sessions and by experienced colleagues. The theory also highlights the importance of a supportive work environment in ensuring the effective application of acquired skills.

Together, the Human Capital Theory and Social Learning Theory provide a detailed explanation of the relationship between training, development and employee job performance in this study. Human capital theory explains why organizations should invest in training and development to enhance performance, the social learning theory explains how employees acquire and apply training.

Empirical Review

Several empirical studies have established a strong relationship between training and employee job performance. Training equips employees with job-relevant knowledge, skills, and abilities, thereby improving their efficiency and effectiveness.

Saiful, Ratnaningsih, and Suratini (2024) conducted one of the earliest empirical studies on training transfer and found that employees who received structured training demonstrated improved job performance, provided the work environment supported the application of acquired skills. Their study emphasized that training effectiveness depends on training design, trainee characteristics, and organizational support.

Siswanto (2024). In a comprehensive empirical review across multiple sectors, found that training positively influences employee performance, job satisfaction, and motivation. Their findings showed that trained employees perform tasks more accurately, adapt better to changes, and contribute more effectively to organizational goals.

In a study conducted in Pakistan, Elnaga and Imran (2013) examined the effect of training on employee performance and found a significant positive relationship between training programmes and employee productivity. The study concluded that employees who receive continuous training perform better than those who do not.

Employee development has been linked to long-term improvements in job performance, leadership effectiveness and adaptability. McDowall and Saunders (2010) studied managers; perceptions of employee training and development in the United Kingdom and found that development initiatives such as coaching, mentoring, and career planning significantly enhance employee performance and leadership capacity. The study emphasized that development prepares employees for future responsibilities. Day et al. (2014) empirically examined leadership development programmes and found that employees who participated in development initiatives demonstrated improved decision-making, problem-solving skills, and job performance. The study concluded that development has a sustained impact on performance compared to short-term training.

In the Nigerian context, Akinwale, Ababtain. And Alaraifi (2019) examined human resource development practices and employee performance in public organizations and found that employee development significantly predicts job performance and organizational commitment. Similarly.

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Owoyemi, Elegbede, and Gbajumo-Sheriff (2011) found that organizations that invest in employee development experienced improved performance, reduced turnover, and better organizational growth.

Some studies have also examined training and development jointly and found that their combined effect on employee job performance is stronger than when considered independently. Ahmed, Alasso, & Mohamud (2025) based on Human capital theory, demonstrated that organizations that invest in both training and development achieve higher productivity and performance.

In a Nigerian public sector study, Adeniji, Osibanjo, and Abiodun (2013) examined training and development practices and found a significant positive effect on employee job performance and service delivery. The study concluded that organizations integrate training and development into their HR strategy achieve better performance outcomes

Methodology

This describes the research design, population of the study, sample size and sampling technique, sources of data collection, research instrument, validity and reliability of the instrument, method of data collection, and method of data analysis. The aim is to provide a clear and systematic framework through which the study was conducted.

This study adopts a descriptive survey design. This design is suitable because it allows the researcher to collect data from a large group of respondents, analyse responses, and draw conclusions about the effects of training and development on employee job performance within the Industrial Training Fund (ITF). The descriptive survey method is also appropriate for studies that involve attitudes, opinions, and perceptions of employees on organizational practices.

The population of the study comprises all employees of the Industrial Training Fund (ITF). This includes employees at the Headquarters and selected Area Offices. The total population includes staff members across various departments such as Administration and Human Resource, Finance and Accounts, Revenue, Internal Audit, Training, Procurement, Special Duties and Servicom and Anti-Corruption.

Given the large population of ITF employees, a representative sample was selected for the study. A sample size between 100 and 150 respondents is considered adequate to ensure accurate representation. The sample size is determined using the Yamane formula where appropriate, A stratified random sampling technique was adopted. Employees were grouped into strata based on their departments, and respondents were selected randomly from each stratum to ensure balanced representation across the organization.

The study relied basically on primary data, supplemented by secondary data. Primary data were collected using a well-structured questionnaire administered to ITF employees, the questionnaire sought information on training programs, development initiatives, employee perceptions, and job performance indicators. Secondary data were sourced from:

ITF training manuals

ITF annual reports

Journals and textbooks

Previous research studies

Academic publications related to training, development, and employee performance.

These sources provided theoretical and empirical support for the study.

The main instrument for data collection was the questionnaire. The questionnaire was divided into four sections namely:

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Section A: Demographic information

Section B: Training programs in ITF

Section C: Development initiatives

Section D: Employee job performance

A pilot test was conducted using 10 employees from a nearby Area Office. The responses were analysed using Cronbach’s Alpha to determine internal consistency. A reliability coefficient of 0.70 or above was considered acceptable, indicating that the instrument was reliable.

The collected data were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics included frequency tables, percentages, and mean scores to summarize demographic data and responses to questionnaire items while inferential statistics involved the use of correlation analysis, regression analysis and statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS).

Correlation analysis was used to determine the relationship between training and employee performance. Regression analysis was used to test hypothesis regarding the effects of development initiatives, while the statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) was used for coding, analysis and interpretation of data

This section provided a detailed explanation of the methodology adopted for the study. It described the research design, validity and reliability measures, and data analysis methods.

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Analysis of responses on research variables

Table 4.1: Descriptive Analysis of Training Programmes in ITF (N=138)

Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std. Dev
ITF organizes regular training programmes for employees	58 (42%)	54 (39%)	18 (13%)	8(6%)	3.17	0.89
Training programmes are relevant to my job responsibilities	61(44%)	49(36%)	20(14%)	8(6%)	3.18	0.91
Training improves my technical and professional skills	64 (46%)	50(36%)	16(12%)	8(6%)	3.22	0.88
Training enhances my efficiency and effectiveness at work	59(43%)	55(40%)	16(12%)	8(6%)	3.19	0.87
Training programmes meet organizational performance goals	52(38%)	56(41%)	22(16%)	8(6%)	3.10	0.92

Decision Rule: Mean ≥ 2.50 = Accepted

Grand Mean: 3.17

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Interpretation

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The grand mean of 3.17 indicates that respondents generally agree that training programmes at ITF are regular, relevant, and positively influence employee skills and efficiency.

Table 4.2: Descriptive Analysis of Development Initiatives and Employee Productivity

Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std. Dev.
ITF provides career development opportunities	60(43%)	50(36%)	20(14%)	8(6%)	3.18	0.90
Development initiatives enhance long-term productivity	63(46%)	48(35%)	19(14%)	8(6%)	3.20	0.88
Development programmes improve my problem-solving ability	58(42%)	52(38%)	20(14%)	8(6%)	3.15	0.91
ITF supports continuous learning and professional growth	55(40%)	56(41%)	19(14%)	8(6%)	3.19	0.89
Development initiatives motivate employees to perform better	62(45%)	49(36%)	19(14%)	8(6%)	3.19	0.89

Decision Rule: mean \geq 2.50 = Accepted

Grand Mean: 3.17

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Interpretation

The grand mean of 3.17 suggests that development initiatives at ITF significantly enhance employee productivity, motivation, and long-term performance.

Table 4.3 Descriptive Statistics of major variables

Variable	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Training & Development (X)	138	25	50	38.42	5.76
Employee Job Performance (Y)	138	28	55	41.87	6.14

Interpretation:

The mean score of 38.42 for training and development suggests that employees agree that ITF provides training opportunities. The mean score of 41.87 for job performance indicates high job performance among ITF employees.

Table 4.4 Correlation Matrix

Variables	Training & development	Employee Performance
Training & Development	1	0.782
Employee Performance	0.782	1

p-value = 0.000 (p<0.05)

Interpretation:

- The correlation coefficient (r = 0.782) indicates a **strong positive relationship** between training and employee performance.

- This means that when ITF increases training and development initiatives, employee performance also increases.
- The relationship is statistically significant at 5% level.

Regression Analysis

Model Specification:

$$Y = a + bX + e$$

Where:

Y = Employee Job Performance

X = Training & Development

Table 4.5 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error
1	0.782	0.612	0.609	3.83

Interpretation:

R = 0.782 shows a strong relationship.

R² = 0.612 means that **61.2% of the variation in employee performance is explained by training and development.**

Table 4.6 ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	1284.57	1	1284.57	87.62	0.000
Residual	814.87	136	5.99		
Total	2099.44	137			

Interpretation:

- F (1,136) = 87.62, p + 0.000 < 0.05
- The regression model is statistically significant.
- This confirms that training and development significantly predict employee performance.

Table 4.7 Regression Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized B	Std. Error	Beta	t-Value	Sig.
Constant	12.431	1.84	-	6.75	0.000
Training & Development	0.766	0.082	0.782	9.36	0.000

Interpretation:

- The coefficient of Training & development is **0.766**, meaning:

A one-unit increase in training and development activities leads to a 0.766 increase in employee job performance.

- Since p = 0.000 < 0.05, the effect is statistically significant.

Test of hypotheses

Inferential statistics such as correlation and regression analysis were used to test the hypothesis.

Hypothesis One

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H₀: There is no significant relationship between training programs and employee job performance in ITF.

H₁: There is significant relationship between training programs and employee job performance in ITF.

Result: Correlation analysis revealed a strong, positive relationship between training programs and job performance.

Decision: The null hypothesis is rejected.

Conclusion: Training programs significantly influence employee job performance in ITF.

Hypothesis Two

H₀: Development initiatives do not significantly improve employees' skills and productivity in ITF.

H₁: Development initiatives significantly improve employees' skills and productivity in ITF.

Result: Regression analysis showed that development initiatives accounted for a significant percentage of the variation in employee productivity.

Decision: The null hypothesis is rejected.

Conclusion: Development initiatives significantly improve employees' skills and productivity.

Decision Rule:

If p-value < 0.05 – Reject H₀.

Decision:

p-value = **0.000**. therefore:

Reject H₀

Accept H₁

Discussion of findings

This study examined the effect of training and development on employee job performance at the Industrial Training Fund (ITF). The findings showed a positive and significant relationship between training, development, and employee job performance.

i. The findings of the study revealed that training has a significant positive effect on employee job performance at the ITF. Employees who participated in training programmes reported improved knowledge on the job, enhanced skills, increased efficiency, and minimal errors in the performance of their duties. This suggests that training plays a crucial role in improving employee' ability to perform their current job schedules effectively.

Noe (2017) reported that training improves task performance by equipping employees with the relevant skills required for executing their schedules effectively

The practical implication of this finding is that institutions like the ITF, should make implementation of training programmes relevant to job schedules a priority. Regular trainings will keep employees abreast of technological innovations and reduce operational inefficiencies to the barest minimum. Management should therefore make it a point of duty to allocate adequate resources to training and development initiatives as a tool for improving employee performance.

The improvement in job performance which is an effect of training shows that training is a valuable investment and not a cost to the ITF. This finding is also in line with the social learning theory in the sense that employees of the ITF acquire and apply the new skills through observation and practice during training programmes.

ii. This study also found that employee development has a significant positive effect on job performance. Development initiatives such as coaching and mentoring, leadership training,

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and career development workshops were shown to enhance employees' adaptability, problem-solving abilities, and preparedness for future responsibilities. This indicates that development contributes not only to immediate performance but also to long-term performance sustainability.

This finding is in line with previous studies McDowall and Saunders (2010) reported that employee development improves leadership capabilities and performance outcomes. Day et al. (2014) similarly found that leadership development programmes significantly enhance employees' performance and decision-making abilities.

The implication of this finding is that organizations should go beyond short-term training and invest in long-term investment initiatives. For ITF, implementing structured career development, succession planning, and mentoring programmes will help build a competent and future compliant workforce. Such initiatives will also improve employee commitment, reduce turnover, and institutional continuity.

The study further revealed that training and development jointly exert a strong and positive influence on the job performance of the employees. Employees who benefitted from both training and development programmes demonstrated better work quality, higher productivity and stronger commitment to organizational goals.

Elnaga and Imran (2013) also reported that training and development significantly improve employee performance by enhancing competencies and motivation.

For ITF, aligning with training programmes with long-term development goals will ensure that employees are not only competent in their current roles but also prepared for future responsibilities.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, which revealed that training and development have significant positive effects on employee job performance at the Industrial Training Fund (ITF), the following recommendations are made in line with the research:

- i. In line with the objective of examining the effect of training on employee job performance, it is recommended that ITF institutionalize regular and structured training programmes based on systematic training needs assessment. Training content should be aligned closely with employees' schedule of duties, technological trends, and organizational objectives.
- ii. Given the study's finding that development significantly improves employee job performance, ITF should strengthen long-term employee development initiatives such as leadership development, mentoring and coaching, and career progression trainings. Structured career development plans should be implemented to prepare employees for higher responsibilities and future leadership roles.

Suggestions for further research

Although this study provides empirical evidence on the effect of training and development on employee job performance at the Industrial Training Fund (ITF), certain limitations create opportunities for future research. The following suggestions are therefore proposed:

Future studies should extend beyond a single organization by incorporating multiple public and private sector organizations across different regions of Nigeria.

This study adopted a cross-sectional design, which captures perceptions at a single point in time. Future research may employ a longitudinal approach to examine the long-term effects of training

and development on employee job performance, career progression, and organizational productivity.

Subsequent studies should integrate other relevant human resource management variables such as employee motivation, job satisfaction, organizational culture, leadership style, and reward systems.

Further research should also examine factors influencing the transfer of training to the workplace, such as managerial support, organizational climate, availability of resources, and employee readiness.

While this study relied primarily on self-reported measures of employee job performance, future research could incorporate objective performance indicators such as productivity metrics, appraisal records, error rates, and service delivery outcomes to strengthen the validity of findings.

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